

Structural, surface morphological and spectroscopic study on cobalt sulphate

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Abstract

The Cobalt Sulphate (CoSO_4) is a transition metal group compound. It is used as a coloring and dehydrating agent in the electroplating and electrochemical industries; as a dehydrated agent for lithographic inks, varnishes, paints, in storage batteries and as a dyeing agent in ceramics, enamels, glazes and porcelain(1,2). In the present study, CoSO_4 has been characterized by EDXA, SEM, XRD and UV-VIS. The EDXA study confirms the elemental composition and SEM analysis has shown almost spherical nature of the particles. The XRD study confirms the crystalline nature of the compound. The UV-VIS reflectance study shows almost constant high reflectance from 190nm to 350nm. Then decreases and reaches low value at 511nm then again decreases. The behavior is almost like trough from 350nm to 750nm. This may be used in optoelectronic applications. The UV-VIS study deduces the energy gap as 2.14 eV and urbach energy value as 0.3158 eV.

Keywords: Cobalt Sulphate, EDXA, SEM, XRD and UV-VIS

References

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